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First record of the wild rice *Oryza meridionalis* in Indonesia

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Oryza meridionalis Ng is an annual diploid ($2n = 2x = 24$) wild species of rice, which has only been reported as endemic to the northern parts of Australia. This wild rice contains the same AA genome as cultivated rice (*O. sativa* L.), and is therefore one of the most accessible genetic resources in the wild rice gene pool for rice improvement. During a recent exploration and collection mission (29 September–9 October 1999) for wild rice species in Irian Jaya, Indonesia, *O. meridionalis* was found and collected at many sites in Merauke District. This is the first record for *O. meridionalis* in Irian

Jaya. *O. meridionalis* was found in swampy lowlands and forests, along canals and ditches, and near or inside farmers' rice fields. According to local farmers, this species occurs abundantly, particularly during the wet season (February–May) when water is sufficient. Farmers call this wild rice *Miyang Padi*, which means “awned rice,” or *Padi Rawa Hitam*, meaning “black swamp rice.” They complain about this wild rice infesting their rice fields and interfering with fishing, which shows the common occurrence of *O. meridionalis* in the area.

The traditional staple food crops in Irian Jaya are mainly sago and tuber crops, such as sweet potato, cassava, and taro. Cultivated rice, introduced into the area only in the early 1980s by transmigrants, is now preferred by many people, particularly those who have moved to Irian Jaya from other parts of the country. The most serious rice insect pests and diseases occurring in this area are whitebacked

planthopper [*Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath)] and rice tungro disease, based on information from the local agriculture extension offices. Because *O. meridionalis* occurs naturally in this area, it might be worthwhile to screen its populations for resistance to these pests. Other wild rice species, such as *O. officinalis*, *O. longiglumis*, and *O. rufipogon*, were also found and collected in Irian Jaya during the expedition. The exploration and collection mission was jointly conducted by IRRI and the Research Institute of Food Crop Biotechnology, CRIFC, AARD, Department of Agriculture of Indonesia.

Influence of unusual weather on pest outbreaks and rice production in Bangladesh

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During the past few years, unusual weather conditions in Bangladesh have directly and indirectly affected rice production. Rice in Bangladesh is grown in four overlapping seasons: *aus* (summer rice), transplanted *aman* (monsoon rice), deepwater rice (mostly floating rice), and *boro* (winter rice). More than 93% of the 2.9 million ha of boro rice is irrigated and is thus less vulnerable to weather calamities. In contrast, transplanted aman, which covers about 5 million ha, is mostly rainfed and is often affected by submergence and drought.

The 1997 transplanted aman crop was affected by a severe drought during the crucial reproductive developmental stage in October. A widespread outbreak of brown planthopper (BPH), *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål), also occurred in October. BPH populations probably built up during August and September, when rainfall was adequate. The drought and BPH outbreak caused localized yield losses of up to 50%

(Left) A panicle of *Oryza meridionalis* collected near Wasur National Park in Merauke District of Irian Jaya, Indonesia. (Below) Farmers helped to collect seed samples from *Oryza meridionalis* plants occurring in their field near Kuprik at Merauke District.

and a 10–15% yield loss in the transplanted aman season nationwide.

The 1998 transplanted aman crop was severely affected by a long-lasting flood, which reduced the rice-cropped area significantly. Widespread outbreaks of rice gall midge, *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason), and sheath blight, caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*, occurred in the early planted higher lands. When the flood peak subsided, farmers transplanted rice in medium-high lands. In some areas, severe outbreaks of rice leaffolders [*Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée), *Marasmia patnalis* (Bradley), and *M. exigua* (Butler)] occurred on late-planted rice fields. A high incidence of BPH and swarming caterpillar, *Spodoptera mauritia* (Boisduval), was also observed in many areas. The 1998 transplanted aman crop suffered 20–25% yield losses from flood and pest outbreaks.

In response to the shortfall in transplanted aman rice production in 1998 and the anticipated increase in rice market price, farmers expanded the boro area in

the following season. Historical data indicated that, after severe floods and loss of transplanted aman rice, farmers met the shortfall by increasing boro rice coverage in the following season (see table).

Recent abnormal weather patterns have perhaps contributed to the unusual outbreaks of BPH, gall midge, leaffolders, and sheath blight in Bangladesh. For insect pests in 1998, ovipositing females may have aggregated in higher elevation rice fields when low-lying fields were flooded. Later generations of adults may have migrated to young rice plants in late-planted fields.

Two other trends might have contributed to the disease and insect problems: the higher use of nitrogenous fertilizers and misuse of insecticides. A positive correlation between levels of N application and sheath blight incidence is often observed because higher N levels result in increased canopy density. It is well established that insecticide misuse can cause outbreaks of some pests, such as BPH, because of the disruption in naturally occurring biological control agents.

BRII will continue to monitor trends in weather patterns and pest outbreaks. If pest outbreaks persist, it may be necessary to change research and rice-breeding priorities in Bangladesh.

Farmer participatory research for rat management in Cambodia

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In 1998, CIAP researchers worked with a local nongovernment organization (CRS) to begin a program of farmer participatory research (FPR) for improved rat management in Svay Teap District of Svay Rieng Province in southeastern Cambodia. The research was compatible with the action research process used by CRS as a way of empowering local farmers to find

Effect of abnormal high floods on boro (winter) rice coverage and production in Bangladesh.^a

Year	Flood situation in previous monsoon	Boro rice area planted to modern varieties		Modern variety boro rice production	
		(ha × 10 ³)	Change over previous year (%)	(t × 10 ⁶)	Change over previous year (%)
1973-74	Normal flood	589	—	1.6	—
1974-75	High flood	659	11.9 ^b	1.6	1.2
1975-76	Normal flood	642	-2.6	1.6	0
1976-77	Normal flood	492	-23.4	1.2	-27.0
1977-78	Normal flood	589	19.7 ¹	1.5	25.2
1978-79	Normal flood	600	1.9	1.4	-7.4
1979-80	Late flood	724	20.7	1.9	36.2
1980-81	Normal flood	747	3.2	2.0	5.8
1981-82	Normal flood	898	20.2	2.5	26.1
1982-83	Normal flood	1,081	20.4	3.0	20.7
1983-84	Normal flood	1,006	-6.9	2.8	-6.6
1984-85	High flood	1,230	22.3	3.4	18.7
1985-86	Normal flood	1,213	-1.4	3.2	-3.9
1986-87	Normal flood	1,340	10.5	3.6	11.8
1987-88	High flood	1,639	22.3	4.3	19.8
1988-89	Very high flood	2,132	30.1	5.4	26.3
1989-90	Normal flood	2,154	1.0	5.7	4.6
1990-91	Normal flood	2,266	5.2	6.0	4.9
1991-92	Normal flood	2,334	3.0	6.4	7.1
1992-93	Normal flood	2,351	0.7	6.2	-2.0
1993-94	Normal flood	2,335	-0.7	6.4	2.9
1994-95	Normal flood	2,410	2.3	6.2	-3.4
1995-96	Normal flood	2,507	4.0	6.8	10.4
1996-97	Normal flood	2,547	1.6	7.1	3.9
1997-98	Normal flood	2,670	4.5	7.8	9.8
1998-99	Very high and long-lasting flood	3,500 ^c	31.1	10.0 ^c	27.9

^aData compiled from *Statistical yearbook of Bangladesh* (published annually), Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics, Dhaka. ^bEarly phase of modern variety boro adoption. ^cTentative estimate.